

Co-Creating Science in Rural Communities

Practical insights from organising a Rural European Researchers' Night in **Armamar, Portugal**

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FULL INFORMATION

Why this matters?

ERN events are mostly urban, held in academic centres, creating unequal access to science for rural and underserved communities.

Portugal is no exception and **ERN events leaving remote territories with little or no opportunity for scientific engagement.**

What we did?

In Armamar, Portugal, we piloted Rural European Researchers' Night (RERN) in 2023 and 2024.

Co-created with local stakeholders, RERN aimed to bring science to rural areas and empower the community to lead inclusive science engagement, creating a replicable model.

How we did it?

8 building blocks for rural science engagement

1
Local co-ownership

2
Students as co-organisers

3
Local ambassadors network

4
“Adopt a Scientist” program

5
Place-based, hands-on activities,
design for dialogue

6
Researcher supports &
incentives

7
Informal & inclusive venues

8
Plan for continuity

Participants' enhanced **scientific literacy**

ARMA-Sci (Rede de Promoção do Capital Científico de Armamar): a **local science NGO**

Community publication: a co-authored book with 62 community voices [3]

Academic advancement: a **PhD scholarship on science education**

Sustainable growth: an expanding event with increasing participation

REFERENCES

[1] Branquinho et al., PLOS SciComm, 2023; [2] Branquinho et al., PLOS SciComm, 2024; [3] Branquinho et al., UA Editora, 2024; [4] Branquinho et al., JCOM, in press, 2025

Reflections & what's next

Could your next science outreach project start in a village like Armamar?

